

success story

EIFFEL tools suite

Iterative integration approach

EIFFEL project implemented and integrated a set of tools that have been demonstrated and refined in the pilot activities of the project. Specifically, horizontal and modular tools have been developed under the project activities **to augment GEOSS data exploration** and **improve the temporal, spatial resolution and data quality of CC related datasets**. Those tools were integrated in an iterative manner, ensuring the validation of the functionality and interoperability of all components and are made available via the EIFFEL [Visualisation engine](#) that acts as an umbrella that concentrates all the key elements of the EIFFEL project. To meet the integration needs of the EIFFEL project, efforts were based **on Scrum, an Agile framework** that is mainly used for software development and focuses on cross-functional teamwork, accountability, and iteration to develop, deliver, and support complex products. The team couldn't know all requirements at the beginning of a project while we acknowledged that evolvement would be guaranteed through experience and continuous learning. This agile approach allowed for an efficient and effective product development; however, the requirement that was constantly driving our efforts was the ease of use, since the software is facing customers. Analysing and designing the product for ease of use, often referred to as **usability and user experience (UX) design**, was focused on the:

- (a) Effectiveness - can users achieve what they need to do using the product;
- (b) Efficiency - how much effort (e.g., time) does it require and;
- (c) Satisfaction - how do they feel about their interaction with the product.

Incorporating gradually the comments and requirements of end-users during the pilot activities, refined the final outcome with the goal of maximizing the potential adoption of EIFFEL's tools and applications.

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

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